

EFFECT OF FOAM SHAPE AND PIEZOELECTRIC MATERIAL PROPERTIES ON THE ELECTROMECHANICAL RESPONSE OF 3-3 PIEZOELECTRIC FOAMS

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1) Introduction

Piezoelectric materials (e.g. lead zirconate titanate, barium titanate) with their unique electromechanical characteristics, have enabled the successful design and fabrication of components for a wide range of applications such as sensors, actuators, ultrasound imagers and hydrophones. The two main approaches that are typically invoked in enhancing the properties of monolithic piezoelectric materials and the devices made of piezoelectric materials are: (i) The additive approach, wherein two or more constituents are added to create several types of piezoelectric composites, thereby enhancing the overall electromechanical response of piezoelectric composites; (ii) The subtractive approach, wherein controlled porosity is introduced in the monolithic materials to create porous piezoelectric materials, thereby enhancing the signal to noise ratios, impedance matching, and piezoelectric figures of merits such as piezoelectric charge coefficients (d_h) and the hydrostatic figures of merit (d_{hg}) and thus making them useful for applications such as hydrophone devices.

Porous piezoelectric materials are classified as 3-0 type (porosity is enclosed in all three dimensions), 3-1 type (porosity exhibits connectivity in 1-direction and the matrix phase is connected in all directions), and 3-3 type (porosity exists in an open interconnecting network where both the porosity and matrix phase exhibits connectivity in all the three dimensions). Several analytical [1-3], numerical [4-10], and experimental [11-14] studies have focused on understanding and characterizing the effect of porosity on the electromechanical response of (zero-dimensional (3-0), one-dimensional (3-1) and three-dimensional (3-3)) porous piezoelectric materials.

Dunn and Taya [1] presented an analytical model to predict the electromechanical response of porous piezoelectric materials with zero-dimensional (3-0) and one-dimensional (3-1) connectivity. Iyer and Venkatesh [4-5] and Kar-Gupta and Venkatesh [6-7] developed finite element models to study porous piezoelectric materials and demonstrated that the porosity shape, orientation, distribution, and connectivity in piezoelectric materials can significantly influence the performance characteristics of zero-dimensional (3-0) and one-dimensional (3-1) porous piezoelectric materials. Bosse et al. [10] developed a unit-cell based finite element model to study the electromechanical response of 3-3 piezoelectric foams and demonstrated that the foam shape and porosity aspect ratio can significantly influence the performance characteristics of 3-3 piezoelectric foams. Nagata et al. [11] synthesized PZT-based piezoelectric materials with 3-3 type interconnected porosity using a modified sintering method and demonstrated that 3-3 type porous materials exhibited improved hydrophone sensitivity and improved output characteristics as compared to that of pore-free PZT materials.

In addition to analytical, numerical, and experimental studies on porous piezoelectric materials, several studies have focused on analysing different piezoelectric materials especially lead-free materials (barium sodium niobate (BNN) [15], barium titanate (BaTiO_3) [16] and relaxor ferroelectrics (RL) [17-20]). For example, Bao et al. [15] synthesized barium sodium niobate using BaCO_3 and Nb_2O_5 in molten NaCl via templated grain growth procedure. Kumar et al. [16] demonstrated enhanced dielectric properties with increase in zirconium contents in barium titanate.

Overall several analytical, numerical and experimental studies have demonstrated that 3-3 type porous piezoelectric materials exhibit a combination of properties that are desirable for practical applications such as hydrophones. However, a comprehensive study of the effect of foam shape and simultaneously piezoelectric material properties in a range of piezoelectric material systems such as barium sodium niobate, barium titanate, and relaxor ferroelectric material on the overall electromechanical response of 3-3 porous piezoelectric foams is not yet available. Hence the objectives of the present study are:

- (i) to develop a unit-cell based finite element model to predict complete elastic, dielectric and piezoelectric properties of 3-3 type piezoelectric foams;
- (ii) to study the effects of foam shape, porosity aspect-ratio, porosity volume fraction and simultaneously the fundamental piezoelectric material properties on the effective electromechanical response of 3-3 type piezoelectric foams;
- (iii) to assess the effects of foam shape, porosity aspect-ratio, porosity volume fraction and simultaneously the fundamental piezoelectric material properties on the effective figures of merit of 3-3 type piezoelectric foams.

2. Classification of Piezoelectric Foam structures

To study the effect of foam shape, and porosity aspect ratio of piezoelectric foams on their effective electromechanical properties, 9 characteristic foam shapes are identified based on their structural aspect ratio and porosity aspect ratio (Figs. 1 and 2).

- (i) The “equiaxed” ($L_1=L_2=L_3$) foam structure (Class II) and cuboidal porosity (with a porosity aspect ratio of 1, $b=a$) is identified as the reference structure.
- (ii) Depending on the variations in the structural aspect ratio of unit cell of foam structure (i.e., less than 1 or greater than 1) along with the poling direction (i.e., 2-direction), we, respectively, identify “longitudinally short” ($L_1=L_3$, $L_2= 0.25L_1$) structures (Class I) or “longitudinally tall” ($L_1=L_3$, $L_2= 1.75 L_1$) structures (Class III).

- (iii) Depending on the variations in the porosity aspect ratio of unit cell of the foam structure (i.e., less than 1 or greater than 1), for each of above mentioned foam structures, we, respectively, identify structures with “flat” (i.e. $b= 0.25a$) or “elongated” porosity (i.e. $b=4a$).

3. Classification of Novel Materials

In order to study the effect of material anisotropy on the effective properties of 3-3 piezoelectric foams, 3 types of novel materials are analysed. Following is the basic description of the materials analyzed in the present study:

3.1 Barium Sodium Niobate (BNN)

Barium sodium niobate exhibits tungsten-bronze structure in which all 15 and 12-fold-coordinated sites are occupied by Ba and Na ions [15]. Single crystal barium sodium niobate exhibits the lowest crystal symmetry of mm2 (orthorhombic crystal class). Table 1 shows elastic, piezoelectric and dielectric properties of single crystal barium sodium niobate.

3.2 Barium Titanate ($BaTiO_3$)

Barium titanate had been shown to exhibit excellent piezoelectric properties and been used in various applications such as multi-layer ceramic capacitors (MLCC), positive temperature coefficient of resistance thermistors, piezoelectric sensors, transducers, actuators and ferroelectric random access memories and electro optic devices [16]. Table 1 shows the properties of single crystal barium titanate. Barium titanate has the highest elastic and dielectric properties along poling direction (i.e. 2-direction) compared to barium sodium niobate and relaxor ferroelectric material. Barium titanate exhibits 4mm (tetragonal crystal class) crystal symmetry.

3.3 Relaxor ferroelectrics ($0.67Pb(Mg_{1/3}Nb_{2/3})O_3-0.33PbTiO_3$)

Due to exceptionally large dielectric permittivity, electrostrictive and piezoelectric parameters, relaxor ferroelectrics was found to have excellent piezoelectric properties [17-20]. Table 1 shows various elastic, electrical and dielectric properties of single crystal relaxor ferroelectrics used in the present study. Single crystal relaxor ferroelectric exhibits 4mm (tetragonal crystal class) crystal symmetry.

4. Constitutive Relations for Piezoelectric Materials

The constitutive relations for a piezoelectric material that exhibits coupling between mechanical and electrical properties are given by:

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{ij} &= C_{ijkl}^E \epsilon_{kl} - e_{ijk} E_k \\ D_i &= e_{ikl} \epsilon_{kl} + \kappa_{ij}^E E_j\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

where σ is second-order stress tensor, ϵ is second-order strain tensor, C^E is fourth-order elasticity tensor with superscript "E" indicating elasticity tensor corresponding to measurement of C at constant/zero electric field, D is electric displacement vector, E is the electric field vector and κ^E is second-order permittivity tensor measured at constant/zero strain. The subscripts i, j, k, l varies from 1 to 6. Eq. (1) is the most general representation of the constitutive behaviour of piezoelectric materials and has 21 elasticity, 18 piezoelectric and 6 permittivity constants that are independent material properties. Thus a complete characterization of piezoelectric foams in the linear elastic domain requires an identification of all 45 independent constants.

5. Finite Element Modelling

A unit cell-based three-dimensional finite element model was developed to determine 45 independent elastic, piezoelectric and dielectric coefficients and the figure of merit of the 3-3 type piezoelectric foam structures over a range of foam shape, porosity aspect-ratio, porosity volume fraction and simultaneously the fundamental piezoelectric material properties using commercially available software ABAQUS. Eight node linear piezoelectric brick elements (C3D8E) are utilized for piezoelectric foam structures where each node is allowed four degrees of freedom (three translational and one electric potential). It is assumed that the piezoelectric material is poled in 2-direction. Various boundary conditions were invoked so that deformation and electric potential across the boundaries of representative unit cell is compatible with deformation of adjacent unit cell [10]. Detailed finite element procedure and boundary conditions are presented in Bosse et al. ([10]).

6. Results and Discussions

Figs. 3 and 4 shows the variation of elastic, piezoelectric and dielectric properties and figures of merit with increasing material volume fraction for 3 different classes (Class I, Class II, Class III) with porosity aspect ratios of $b=0.25a$, $b=a$ and $b=4a$ and material anisotropy. The following observations can be made.

- (i) Elastic, piezoelectric and dielectric properties increase non-linearly with increasing material volume fraction for all material. In general, barium titanate exhibits higher dielectric constants (κ_{22}) in longitudinal direction (parallel to poling direction) as compared to barium sodium niobate and relaxor ferroelectrics. For example, at 62% material volume fraction, the fundamental dielectric constant, κ_{22} for barium titanate is $0.922E-08 \text{ C}^2/\text{Nm}^2$ and κ_{22} for barium sodium niobate and relaxor ferroelectric are $0.16E-08 \text{ C}^2/\text{Nm}^2$ and $0.37E-08 \text{ C}^2/\text{Nm}^2$ respectively for equiaxed structure (i.e. Class II with $L1=L2=L3$) with elongated porosity aspect ratio (with $b=4a$). In transverse direction (i.e. perpendicular to poling direction), barium sodium niobate exhibits highest elastic constants in 1-direction (C_{11}) as compared to barium titanate and relaxor ferroelectrics.
- (ii) For foam structures made of barium sodium niobate and barium titanate, the principal electromechanical properties in transverse direction (perpendicular to poling direction) such as C_{11} , and κ_{11} are higher for foam structure with flat cuboidal porosity (i.e. $b=0.25a$) as compared to cuboidal and elongated cuboidal porosity (i.e. $b=a$, or $b=4a$) whereas in longitudinal direction (parallel to poling direction) electromechanical properties such as C_{22} , κ_{22} and e_{22} are equal or higher for foam structures with elongated porosity (i.e. $b=4a$) as compared to lower porosity aspect ratios i.e. $b=0.25a$ (flat cuboidal) and $b=a$ (cuboidal). On the other hand for relaxor ferroelectrics, elastic properties in transverse and longitudinal direction i.e. C_{11} and C_{22} respectively, are higher for cuboidal porosity aspect ratio (i.e. $b=a$) compared to flat-cuboidal (i.e. $b=0.25a$) and elongated cuboidal (i.e. $b=4a$) porosity aspect ratios for all classes except Class I, the elastic constant C_{11} are high for flat-cuboidal porosity

aspect ratio (i.e. $b=0.25a$) compared to other porosity aspect ratios).

- (iii) In general, the figures of merits such as piezoelectric charge coefficient (d_h), the piezoelectric voltage coefficient (g_h) and the hydrostatic figure of merit ($d_h g_h$) for foams structures made of different piezoelectric materials can be enhanced significantly by changing the structural aspect ratio and porosity aspect ratio (Fig. 4). For example, at 70% material volume fraction, d_h , g_h , and $d_h g_h$ are, respectively, increased by 21%, 360%, 457% for barium sodium niobate, 75%, 548%, 1037% for barium titanate and 12%, 221% and 259% for relaxor ferroelectrics by changing shape of the porosity for equiaxed foam ($L1=L2=L3$) structure (Class II) from a cuboidal shape (i.e. $b=a$) to a flat-cuboidal (i.e. $b=0.25a$).
- (iv) Piezoelectric coupling constant (K_t) for the foam structures have shown increase with increase in porosity volume fractions. By inducing porosity in all materials, relaxor ferroelectric has shown maximum increase of 51% in piezoelectric coupling constant (K_t) whereas barium sodium niobate (BNN) has lowest increase of only 7.6%. At about 97 % porosity volume fraction for equiaxed ($L1=L2=L3$) foam structure (Class II) with cuboidal porosity shape (i.e. $b=a$), relaxor ferroelectrics exhibit highest piezoelectric coupling constant ($K_t \sim 0.954$), barium sodium niobate exhibits lowest piezoelectric constant ($K_t \sim 0.240$), and barium titanate showed intermediate behaviour with ($K_t \sim 0.442$).

7. Conclusions

Porous piezoelectric materials, especially 3-3 type porous piezoelectric materials exhibit a combination of properties that are desirable for certain practical applications such as hydrophones. However, a comprehensive study of the effect of foam microstructural features and simultaneously material anisotropy on the overall response of 3-3 piezoelectric foam structures is not yet available. Hence, the present study is focused on developing a comprehensive understanding of the effect of foam shape, porosity aspect-ratio, porosity volume fraction and simultaneously the fundamental piezoelectric material properties in a range of piezoelectric material systems such as barium sodium niobate, barium titanate, and relaxor

ferroelectric material on the effective electromechanical response of 3-3 type piezoelectric foams. Among the materials analyzed, relaxor ferroelectrics have shown to have the highest figures of merits (i.e., K_t , d_h , g_h and $d_h g_h$) and foam structures made of relaxor ferroelectric are suitable for applications such as hydrophones. At 91.1 % porosity volume fraction, longitudinally short (i.e. Class I with $L2=0.25L1$) foam structure with flat-cuboidal shape (i.e. $b=0.25a$) porosity, the K_t , d_h , g_h and $d_h g_h$ are respectively 0.9524, 2.55E-09 m/V, 40.1 Vm/N and 1E-07 m²/N for foam structure made of relaxor ferroelectric material.

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Table 1. Fundamental properties of three different novel materials analyzed (barium sodium niobate (BNN), barium titanate (BaTiO₃) and relaxor ferroelectrics (RL)).

	Barium sodium Niobate (BNN) ($\rho=5300$ Kg/m ³)	Barium titanate (BaTiO ₃) ($\rho=5700$ kg/m ³)	Relaxor ferroelectric material ($\rho=8060$ Kg/m ³)
C_{11}^E (GPa)	238.9	150.4	115
C_{12}^E (GPa)	50.06	65.94	102
C_{13}^E (GPa)	104.2	65.6	103
C_{22}^E (GPa)	135.1	145.5	103
C_{23}^E (GPa)	52.14	65.94	102
C_{33}^E (GPa)	247.4	150.4	115
C_{44}^E (GPa)	64.94	43.86	69
C_{55}^E (GPa)	75.76	42.37	66
C_{66}^E (GPa)	65.79	43.86	69
e_{16} (C/m ²)	2.763	11.40	10.1
e_{21} (C/m ²)	-0.445	-4.320	-3.9
e_{22} (C/m ²)	4.335	17.40	20.3
e_{23} (C/m ²)	-0.285	-4.320	-3.9
e_{34} (C/m ²)	3.377	11.40	10.1
κ_{11}^ϵ (10 ⁻⁹ C ² /Nm ²)	2.081	12.80	12.7
κ_{22}^ϵ (10 ⁻⁹ C ² /Nm ²)	2.656	15.10	6.02
κ_{33}^ϵ (10 ⁻⁹ C ² /Nm ²)	2.187	12.80	12.7

Fig. 1. Schematic illustrating three classes of piezoelectric foam structures: (a) longitudinally short structure (Class I); (b) equiaxed structure (Class II); and (c) longitudinally tall structure (Class III) for all three materials (barium sodium niobate (BNN), barium titanate (BaTiO₃), and relaxor ferroelectrics (RL)).

Fig. 2. Schematic illustrating 9 piezoelectric foam structures based on structural aspect ratio and porosity aspect ratio for three different classes (Class I, Class II, and Class III).

Fig. 3. Variation of the fundamental, elastic, dielectric and piezoelectric properties of three different classes (Class I, Class II and Class III), each with three porosity shapes of piezoelectric foam structures with respect to material volume fraction for different novel materials; (a) barium sodium niobate (BNN) (b) barium titanate (BaTiO₃) and (c) relaxor ferroelectrics (RL)

Fig. 4. Variation of the figures of merits of three different classes (Class I, Class II and Class III), each with three porosity shapes of piezoelectric foam structures with respect to material volume fraction for three different novel materials; (a) barium sodium niobate (BNN) (b) barium titanate (BaTiO₃) and (c) relaxor ferroelectrics (RL).